

A study on enzymatic hydrolysis of fruit and vegetable waste using waste activated sludge

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Abstract : A rise in demand for renewable sources of energy, coupled with the uncontrolled rate in the generation of municipal solid waste (MSW) have led to the development of anaerobic digestion (AD) for stabilizing organic fraction of the municipal solid waste (OFMSW). It is well established from past studies that enhancement in the overall AD process can be achieved by improving the rate-limiting hydrolytic phase. The present study focused on improving the degree of hydrolysis of fruit and vegetable waste (FVW), which occupy a more than 60% of the generated OFMSW, by addition of waste activated sludge (WAS). The enzymatic action of the biomass present in the WAS brought about considerable enhancement in the hydrolysis of FVW with over 92% reduction in weight within 216 h from the onset of hydrolysis. In this regard, the size of the FVW as well as the amount of WAS added played significant roles.

Keywords : AD, OFMSW, waste activated sludge (WAS), fruit and vegetable waste (FVW), enzymatic hydrolysis, lignocellulose.

I. Introduction

The uncontrolled rate at which municipal solid wastes (MSW) continue to generate from different municipalities worldwide has led to the development of the various existing municipal solid waste management (MSWM) strategies. As such, not only the classical MSWM techniques (such as, sanitary landfilling, composting, and incineration/pyrolysis) have been replaced by anaerobic digestion (AD), but there has been substantial improvement in the AD process itself¹. Studies have shown that the major fraction of the generated MSW comprises mainly of organic matter (60–70%), of which food waste (FW) and fruit and vegetable waste (FVW) are the primary constituents. It was reported in a study by Kim *et al.*,² that 15–63% of the MSW generated worldwide constitutes of FW. Under this scenario, the application of various enzymes in enhancing the rate-limiting hydrolytic phase of the AD process is being viewed with even greater interest. AD is a biochemical process where breakdown of the complex organic

matters or polymers to simple soluble organic matters or monomers is mediated by fermentative group of bacteria via hydrolysis, followed by the conversion of the monomers into long chain fatty acids (LCFAs), short chain fatty acids (SCFAs) and alcohols via acidogenesis, and finally conversion of the acetate, alcohols and H₂ plus CO₂ into CH₄ and CO₂ via methanogenesis.

The biodegradable polymers in OFMSW include lignocelluloses, proteins, lipids and starch. The depolymerization of these organic polymers is carried out by specialized microbial population of the fermentative bacteria. Being a complex process, the hydrolysis phase is considered to be the rate-limiting step in the overall AD process. The liquefaction of the lignocelluloses in OFMSW into simple monomers via enzymatic action of fermentative bacteria, as mentioned above, is defined as enzymatic hydrolysis. Enzymatic hydrolysis is essential since it speeds up the degradation of the complex lignocellulosic substrates, which are otherwise difficult to degrade.

Lignocellulosic biomass consists of cellulose (38–50%), hemicelluloses (23–32%), lignin (15–25%), and small amounts of extractives^{3,4}. These components form the lignocellulosic matrix by strongly inter meshing and bonding through covalent or non-covalent bonds. The conversion of lignocellulosic materials via enzymatic hydrolysis includes two major processes : hydrolysis of the cellulose fraction, present in the lignocellulosic materials, to fermentable sugars (monosaccharides), and fermentation of sugars to ethanol (alcohol). Enzymes catalyze the hydrolytic phase, whereas the fermentation is carried out by different bacteria.

The important steps that are involved in the enzymatic hydrolysis of the lignocellulosic matter include : (1) transfer of the enzyme from the bulk aqueous surface to the surface of the lignocellulosic particles, (2) adsorption of the enzyme, and subsequent formation of enzyme-substrate-complexes (ES), (3) hydrolysis of lignocellulose, (4) transfer of lignocellulosic material (cellodextrins, glucose, cellobiose) from the surface of the substrate into the bulk aqueous phase, and (5) subsequent hydrolysis of the transferred lignocellulosic materials in the aqueous phase⁵. Among these steps, the adsorption of enzymes and the subsequent formation of ES complexes are regarded to be the most vital in the enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic substrates^{6–8}. Beside the effectiveness of the enzymes, the physical, chemical and morphological characteristics of the lignocelluloses play important roles during the enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocelluloses. In other words, hydrolyzing lignocellulose to fermentable monosaccharides is a technical problem due to the digestability of cellulose. A better understanding of the physico-chemical, structural and compositional factors of cellulose may be productive in improving its overall digestability. In this regard, it is essential to adopt various pretreatment techniques for obtaining fermentable sugars/monosaccharides in the hydrolysis step⁹.

The enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic materials can thus be sub-divided into two main factors : enzyme related factors, which mainly focus on improving the enzyme related activity; and substrate

related factors, which concentrate on improving the accessibility of enzymes to lignocelluloses⁴. The accessibility of enzymes to lignocelluloses depends on the crystallinity of the cellulose present, the contents and distributions of lignin and hemicelluloses in the OFMSW, and the surface area available⁹. Pretreatment breaks down the interaction of hemicelluloses and lignin with cellulose, and disrupts the crystalline structure of cellulose so that the accessibility of enzymes into the cellulose gets enhanced during the hydrolysis step¹⁰. A considerable amount of cellulose generally exists in the crystalline form, which are extremely resistant to chemical and biological hydrolysis. Due to the large size of the cellulase enzymes (3–18 nm), they can only degrade the cellulose crystal from its surfaces resulting in low enzymatic hydrolysis rates¹¹. However, if the crystalline cellulose is converted to amorphous form via pretreatment⁴, it can be easily hydrolyzed by the cellulase enzymes.

The low enzymatic hydrolysis rates of raw materials present in OFMSW is on account of the existence of hemicelluloses and lignin, which impede the contact of enzymes with cellulose¹². In addition, the presence of non-productive binding of enzymes to lignin also inhibits the hydrolysis of cellulose¹². Hence, the pretreatment strategies should be aimed at removing the lignin and hemicelluloses so that the overall pore size as well as the accessible surface area of the lignocellulosic materials increases, reducing the non-productive adsorption of enzymes to lignin^{13,14}. Application of various pretreatment techniques reduce the recalcitrance of lignocellulosic materials by removing lignin and hemicelluloses and results in significant improvement of the lignocellulosic digestability⁴.

The accessible specific surface area of the lignocellulosic materials plays a crucial role in affecting the rate of enzymatic hydrolysis. The accessible specific surface area of lignocellulosic materials greatly depends on the particle size and porosity (pore volume). By the reduction of the lignocellulosic particle size, the rate of enzymatic hydrolysis and consequently the yield of glucose can be improved¹⁵. This

is on account of the dispersion of the lignocellulosic materials into nanoscale, which ultimately results in the dramatic increase of their specific surface area. This in turn causes rapid breakdown of almost all the cellulose particles, coming in contact with the enzymes within a very short time¹⁶. The porosity of lignocellulosic materials is thus linearly correlated with its enzymatic hydrolysis^{4,9}.

The popular pretreatment techniques that enhance the rate of enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocellulosic materials are as follows : (1) physical pretreatments, such as mechanical comminution (chipping, grinding, shredding, or milling) and irradiation (gamma rays, electron beam or microwave); (2) chemical pretreatments, such as alkali pretreatment, acid pretreatment, oxidative delignification, organosolv process, and ionic liquids pretreatments; (3) physico-chemical pretreatments, such as steam explosion, hydrothermal pretreatment, ammonia fiber explosion, supercritical CO₂ pretreatment; (4) biological pretreatments, such as application of various enzymes (laccase, lignin peroxidases and manganese peroxidases) and bacteria/microorganisms (white-rot, brown-rot and soft-rot fungi). All these pretreatment techniques aim to reduce the recalcitrance of lignocellulose to enzymes by : lowering the content of lignin and hemicelluloses, increasing the accessible surface area, reducing the crystallinity of cellulose, increasing the porosity, and altering the lignin structure⁴.

The present study has been aimed to determine the viability of using waste activated sludge (WAS) towards enhancing the hydrolysis of FVW. It has been observed from past studies that the rate of hydrolysis of OFMSW gets significantly enhanced when combined with sewage sludge¹⁷⁻¹⁹. In addition, the suitability of FVW to undergo AD, has been also explored with due consideration by performing physical characterization on composite basis.

II. Materials and methods

A. Acclimation of the aerobic biomass

The acclimation of the aerobic biomass was done in a bucket of 10 L volume. For this purpose, sew-

age sludge was collected from a lab-scale hybrid aerobic bioreactor treating wastewater, and the collected sludge was cultured in the aforesaid 10 L volume bucket at the Environmental Engineering Laboratory of Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology, Shibpur (IESTS) for 3 to 4 months. The Mixed Liquor Suspended Solids (MLSS) concentration was continuously regulated at 12040 mg/L, and the total liquid volume in the bucket was maintained at 9 L. In order to maintain the MLSS concentration, regular feeding of the biomass was ensured by addition of 1 L synthetic feed solution, which comprised 10 g of anhydrous dextrose-D, 0.43 g of potassium di-hydrogen phosphate and 2.85 g of ammonium nitrate. Suitably 1 L of supernatant was removed every time prior to addition of the synthetic feed. In addition, nutrients in the form of phosphate buffer, ferric chloride, magnesium sulfate and calcium chloride, 10 mL each, were also added. For the purpose of aeration, two numbers of single motor-fitted aquarium pumps were used. The pH of the WAS was maintained in the range of 7.1–7.5.

B. Characterization of FVW

FVW was procured from the guest house kitchen of IESTS. Thereafter, physical characterization of the procured FVW was carried out on composite basis. This was done by homogenizing the procured FVW fraction, and uniformly separating the homogenized content into several sets so that the various key physical parameters, such as specific gravity, bulk density, fixed solids, volatile solids, loss of moisture and moisture content can be determined. The bulk density and specific gravity was measured by water displacement method. The loss of moisture, moisture content, fixed solids and volatile solids were measured in accordance with the method mentioned by Tchobanoglous *et al.*,²⁰. Numerous runs, of which 10 numbers of runs have been tabulated, were carried out for determining the physical characteristics of FVW.

C. Experimental plan of the hydrolysis study

Following characterization, the procured fraction of the FVW was manually sorted in order to remove the non-biodegradable organic fractions of the fruits

and vegetables. Thereafter, the sorted fraction was chopped into small pieces of thickness ranging from 30 to 40 mm using kitchen knife. The chopped FVW was then divided into 6 fractions of 1 kg each. 6 nylon bags were then filled up with those chopped fractions. The 6 nylon bags, containing 1 kg of FVW, were then placed in 6 different buckets having variable WAS content (on mg/g basis). In order for the nylon bags to remain in complete contact with the biomass, during the entire period of hydrolysis, concrete frustums were placed over each bag. The FVW to WAS ratios in the 6 buckets were set in the following proportions : (1) 12040 : 1000 (12040 mg of WAS + 1000 g of FVW); (2) 14540 : 1000 (14540 mg of WAS + 1000 g of FVW), (3) 17040 : 1000 (17040 mg of WAS + 1000 g of FVW), (4) 19540 : 1000 (19540 mg of WAS + 1000 g of FVW), (5) 22040 : 1000 (22040 mg of WAS + 1000 g of FVW), and (6) 0 : 1000 (2 L tap water + 1000 g of FVW). The final liquid volume in each bucket was kept at 2 L. The 6 buckets were then placed inside a wooden chamber, where the temperature was constantly maintained at $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, for 216 h to undergo hydrolysis.

The hydrolysis study was based on four different parameters namely, weight, pH, COD and VFA, which were measured at a minimum of 24 h interval. The initial reading was taken in between the 45th

min and 1 h, past the time from when the buckets, filled with FVW and WAS, were placed inside the wooden chamber. The reduction in weight of the hydrolyzed FVW fraction present in each of the nylon bags was carefully measured by squeezing out the liquid portion from the nylon bags, before taking the weight. For the purpose of measuring the remaining parameters, sample was collected from each of the buckets. Before collecting the sample from one of the buckets, the squeezed out liquid fraction from the nylon bag was mixed thoroughly with the content present in the bucket using a glass stirrer. Then the pH units of the collected raw samples were measured. Thereafter the raw samples were filtered and then diluted to a suitable extent (approximately 30 times) before measuring the COD and the VFA. For the purpose of measuring the pH, and the COD, the procedures described in the Standard Methods²¹ were followed. The VFA was measured in accordance with the ferric hydroxamate method, described by Chatterjee *et al.*²², using a single-beam spectrophotometer.

III. Results and discussion

A. Characterization of FVW

The suitability of the procured FVW to undergo hydrolysis was asserted from the characterization results, tabulated below in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical characterization results of FVW

Run No.	Specific gravity	Bulk density (kg/m^3)	Loss of moisture (%)	Moisture content (%)	Fixed solids (%)	Volatile solids (%)
Run 1	1.073	1073	21.67	91.00	14.00	86.00
Run 2	1.008	1008	18.54	93.00	3.50	96.50
Run 3	1.004	1004	34.00	87.00	2.00	98.00
Run 4	0.949	949	36.00	89.00	4.00	96.00
Run 5	1.176	1176	28.00	87.50	6.00	94.00
Run 6	1.101	1101	26.50	90.00	8.50	91.50
Run 7	1.111	1111	25.67	91.00	7.50	92.50
Run 8	1.071	1071	29.00	86.50	6.00	94.00
Run 9	0.941	941	31.00	78.50	3.00	97.00
Run 10	0.923	923	30.00	82.00	2.50	97.50
Mean	1.036	1036	28.038	87.55	5.70	94.30
Variance	0.0063	6321.4	25.122	17.573	11.91	11.91
Standard deviation	0.0795	79.507	5.012	4.192	3.451	3.451

It can be observed that the FVW procured from the guest house kitchen of IESTS had an average moisture content of over 87% and volatile solids content of over 94%, which are suitable characteristics for the occurrence of hydrolysis^{20,21}. In addition, it can be also observed that during the three instances (Run 10, Run 9 and Run 4) when the collected sample of FVW had a specific gravity below 1.000, the corresponding loss of moisture as well as the moisture content were on the lower sides, with Run 9 showing the lowest moisture content, among all the calculated values for loss of moisture and moisture content. However, the corresponding VS contents for those three runs were found to be on the higher side among all the calculated VS percentages. This evidently suggested that with the increase in moisture content the bulk density of FVW rose and, more often than not the moisture content of the generated FVW remained to such an extent, which ensured the bulk density to remain over 1000 kg/m³³⁰.

In this regard, it has to be kept in mind that seasonal variations may have an impact on bulk density and moisture content of the generated FVW. The present study was carried out in the summer months. Variations in bulk density as well as in moisture content have to be found out for other seasons as well. On the other hand, it can be also concluded that the variations in the VS content of FVW greatly depended on the type of individual fruits and vegetables present in the composite fraction. A separate characterization of the FVW waste on individual basis³⁰ should ascertain this change, with regards to VS content, which has been reflected in the present study.

B. Hydrolysis study

The enzymatic properties of WAS in the rapid degradation of FVW have been well documented in various past studies^{23,24}. As such, in the present study the enzymatic properties of WAS in enhancing the hydrolysis of FVW was demonstrated by measuring the changes in weight, pH, VFA and COD.

B.1. Percentage hydrolysis profile

The reduction in weight of the FVW, following hydrolysis, was expressed as percentage hydrolysis.

It can be observed from the percentage-hydrolysis profile shown in Fig. 1 that the percentage reduction in weight or the degree of hydrolysis of the FVW fraction subjected to hydrolysis, for the duration of 216 h, gradually improved with the increase in WAS content up to 22040 mg. This indicated that with the increase in WAS content, the corresponding enzymatic action of the WAS in enhancing the degree of FVW hydrolysis kept on improving. It is well established that a certain fraction of the FVW is usually made up of complex organic C-chains, the breakdown of which necessitates either a stronger enzymatic action or other types of advanced pretreatment (thermal, chemical, mechanical) techniques prior to the start of the main AD process.

As such, it can be seen from the percentage hy-

Fig. 1. Percentage hydrolysis profile for different proportions of WAS and FVW.

drolysis profile that the maximum reduction in weight achieved for the different proportions of WAS added was around 90% and, the lowest reduction in weight was unsurprisingly in the bucket devoid of WAS. Perhaps, complete breakdown of the FVW fraction would have been possible with the application of a stronger enzyme, capable of degrading hemicelluloses and lignin. In addition, it can be observed that the percentage hydrolysis in the bucket devoid of WAS was the lowest to start with. However, the microbes present in the added tap-water and in the FVW itself enhanced the reduction in weight, once the complex organic C-chains were broken. With the addition of WAS, the breakdown of the complex or-

ganic C-chains was accelerated. Since, past studies have deemed FVW to be a cellulose-poor waste^{25,26}, a weak enzyme such as that of WAS sufficed in the desirable enhancement of the hydrolysis process.

B.2. pH profile

The pH profile in Fig. 2 shows a consistent trend of the pH becoming steady, following the onset of acidogenesis. It can be observed that the pH, immediately after the onset of the hydrolysis, remained mostly above 6.00, indicating slow degradation of the FVW fraction. Exactly 24 to 36 h later, the pH fell below 5.00, pointing steady occurrence of hydrolysis. 96 to 120 h later, the pH values were observed to increase above 5.00, indicating the onset of acidogenesis. This remained mostly steady for the remainder of the hydrolysis duration confirming that there was no further significant formation of LCFAs, which are mostly responsible for the lowering of pH below 5.00, and that the long C-chain VFAs (butyric acid, valeric acid, propionic acid) were dominant. It was also observed that the proportion of WAS didn't have any significant influence on the pH values.

Fig. 2. pH profile for different proportions of FVW and WAS.

The pH profile is mostly influenced by the nature of the waste undergoing hydrolysis. FVW, which is characterized by the presence of significantly large amounts of organic acids and alcohols, lowers the pH units to as little as 4.00 upon hydrolysis. The degree of hydrolysis primarily depends on the ac-

cessibility of the finer particles to the enzymes (WAS). The finer particles become accessible once the complex substrates are "peeled" off from the surfaces. The presence of finer particles results in the overall increase of the surface area for the microbes to carry out enzymatic hydrolysis. The greater the particulate matter surface area accessible to the microbes, the greater the degree of hydrolysis²⁷.

In addition to the surface area of the particulate matter accessible to the microbes, the operating temperature at which the hydrolysis is being carried out is also equally important. Higher operating temperatures enable rapid liquefaction of the fibrous FVW portion^{28,29}. With enhancement in the degree of hydrolysis of FVW, there is a subsequent increase in the amount of LCFAs and alcohol formation. The faster the aforesaid phenomena occur, the faster the drop in pH units.

B.3. COD profile

Soluble COD (sCOD) values were measured, via closed reflux method, after filtering and diluting the collected sample. The sCOD profile was obtained by plotting the sCOD readings against time. It can be seen from the sCOD profile in Fig. 3 that initially with the onset of hydrolysis the sCOD increased sharply, indicating the breakdown/solubilization of the easily biodegradable fractions present in the FVW. Thereafter, the sCOD values slowly decreased, indicating the utilization of the produced sCOD by the hydrolytic microbes present in the buckets. At the

Fig. 3. sCOD profile for different proportions of WAS and FVW.

end, however, there was again an increase in the sCOD values, indicating the degradation/solubilization of the complex fraction present in the FVW due to the action of the aerobic biomass. Once the easily biodegradable fractions present in the FVW got hydrolyzed initially, enzymes secreted by the biomass brought about degradation of the complex fractions present in the FVW. This is basically observed from the plotted sCOD profile, where the increase in the sCOD values had occurred for the second time (initially there was a sharp increase) mostly after the 150th h.

The lowest sCOD values were observed in the bucket with 19540 mg (highest) WAS content. In case of the bucket devoid of WAS, the sCOD generated for the second time remained unconsumed. This implied that the microorganisms that were present in FVW and tap-water during the onset of the hydrolysis were capable of consuming the sCOD only in the initial phase following which no reduction in sCOD occurred. On the other hand, the biomass present in WAS continued consuming the sCOD generated even after the 150th h. This was main the reason why the remaining five buckets showed similar sCOD reduction trend.

Thus, it can be safe to assume that the presence of WAS would have facilitated in the further breakdown/solubilization of the particulate organic matter present in the FVW, after consumption of the sCOD that was produced after the 150th h mark, if the hydrolysis period were lengthened.

However, this would not have been possible in the bucket devoid of WAS since it didn't have any biomass to carry out the enzymatic hydrolysis. It can also be said that initially the consumption of the generated sCOD had been on account of the bacteria and microbes present in the tap water and FVW itself, and it is only after the generation of the sCOD, past the 150th h mark, that the enzymatic properties of the aerobic biomass were better observed.

B.4. VFA profile

It can be observed from Fig. 4 that initially, till the 36th h, the VFA concentrations gradually increased with time. This point in time where the VFA

concentrations had maximized was same for all the six buckets, confirming that the time taken for the maximum initial degradation of the FVW to organic acids was more dependent on the nature of the FVW. The extent of degradation, however, depended on the quantity of WAS present. The more easily the outer surface of the substrates decomposed, the more rapid was the generation of the VFAs. In addition, it can be also observed that after reaching the maximum concentration, the VFAs steadily degraded only to increase one final time before decreasing again. During the mid-stages (72–144 h), the decrease in concentrations of the VFAs was due to the conversion of the same into hydrogen, carbon dioxide and other gaseous products.

The sudden spike in the VFA concentrations just before the end of each trial was mainly due to the breakdown of the slow-degrading organic fraction present in the FVW. In the absence of any slow-degrading/complex organic fraction no spike in VFA concentrations were observed. Hence, the extent of the spike in VFA concentrations before the completion of the hydrolysis period can be related to the nature of the FVW undergoing hydrolysis, and the concentration of the WAS present in each bucket.

It can be observed from VFA profile that during both the instances when the VFA concentrations in the 6 buckets spiked up, the highest spikes were noticed in case of the two buckets where the content of WAS were relatively greater than the remaining

Fig. 4. VFA profile for different proportions of WAS and FVW.

4. In the buckets devoid of WAS content and the lowest WAS content the initial spike in VFA concentrations were the least. Since the degree of generation of the VFAs was dependent on the enzymatic action of the biomass present in the WAS added, the bucket devoid of WAS had the smallest initial spike (in VFA concentrations) followed by the bucket with the least WAS content. Had it been a cellulose-rich substrate instead of FVW, stronger enzymes would have been needed to carry out degradation.

IV. Conclusion

The enhancement in the degree of FVW hydrolysis following the application of WAS has been clearly asserted. The increased rate of solubilization (observed from percentage hydrolysis) coupled with the generation of large concentrations of VFAs and sCOD point towards the enzymatic potentiality of microbes present in WAS. However, the utility of WAS in enhancing the hydrolysis of other complex fractions of MSW, rich in lignocellulosic biomass (e.g. yard trimmings), have to be explored. FVW being a cellulose-poor substrate usually undergo hydrolysis very easily in the initial stages. It is only in the later stages that the efficacy of using WAS comes into light. The role of various other enzymes, such as cellulase, amylase, pectinase and xylanase, in the enzymatic hydrolysis of OFMSW are also needed to be explored given the diverse composition of organic substrates in OFMSW. This can be achieved by co-culturing two or more microbes capable of producing the aforesaid enzymes, and this strategy of speeding up the hydrolysis stage by microbial co-culture has been already implemented in the AD of agricultural waste.

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